

Vasile Cucerescu*

INNOVATION AND KNOWLEDGE DIPLOMACY – THE NEW DIMENSION OF EXTERNAL RELATIONS

Abstract

Building its relations with external partners, the European Union strives to develop the most adequate capabilities for economic growth and for higher quality of life in Europe. In the new century of global competition, the expanding role of knowledge diplomacy in international politics affects and implies the European Union. In view of the fact that the effective use of scientific knowledge in external relations is highly important, this epistemic community can provide value-based legal, economic, diplomatic and cultural foundations for sustainable development and growth in the European Union. The research considers the layers of knowledge society in which knowledge diplomacy in external relations plays an important role for moving innovations in and out of national economies of the European Union; new diplomacy that resembles knowledge management, i.e. knowledge management is used in diplomacy; the political actors that witness a profound transformation of diplomacy, including a paradigm shift, because economic diplomacy is not self-sufficient for global competition, for free movement of knowledge, results and innovations; a fissure that is to be tackled by know-how diplomacy for reinforcing innovative tools in international relations; new diplomacy that pleads for an open diplomacy contributing and supporting knowledge economy; and how knowledge diplomacy is conducive to smart growth of Europe's societies.

Keywords: the European Union, external/international relations, development, innovation, knowledge society, knowledge economy, knowledge diplomacy

Introduction

The European Union became an undisputed world actor and power, although it is not yet a political union in the classical meaning of the concept. The European Union's growing role on the international arena and in international relations requires new

*Department of International Law, International Relations Institute of Moldova; vasile.cucerescu@ymail.com

abilities and capabilities which are different from those of the Members States in terms of geopolitics and diplomatic law. Diplomatic law as an area of international law also considers new practices which would fit realities in the era of globalization. Diplomacy needs adequate competences and innovative approaches in handling affairs, because the world is changing rapidly, international relations are developing, new threats evolve and specific tools need to be improved. Moreover, traditional diplomacy should serve just as a basis for modern diplomacy. Innovations should infuse the art and practice of diplomacy in a knowledge-based society.

The research aims at analyzing to what extent innovation and knowledge diplomacy rise to the new dimension of external relations. In doing that, key concepts are to be clarified, such as: innovation, knowledge, knowledge society, knowledge management, knowledge economy, knowledge diplomacy.

The basic notion that is of great scientific significance is the term *knowledge*. There are many definitions to knowledge, but a recent one tries to synthesize previous undertakings. It says that “knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates and is applied in the minds of knowers. In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories, but also in organizational routines, processes, practices, and norms” (Davenport, Prusak 2000: 5). In other words, it pertains to information and experiences at the level of epistemic communities, norms, processes and human practices. Knowledge is a human act and it is socially constructed. Knowledge is a part of the human act of knowing, tacit as well as explicit, social as well as individual, and dynamic.

As for the term knowledge society, which is frequently used, a definition was proposed by P.F. Drucker, who argues that “in the knowledge society, clearly, more and more knowledge, and especially advanced knowledge, will be acquired well past the age of formal schooling and increasingly, perhaps, through educational processes that do not center on the traditional school. But at the same time, the performance of the schools and the basic values of the schools will be of increasing concern to society as a whole, rather than being considered professional matters that can safely be left to educators. We can also predict with confidence that we will redefine what it means to be an educated person. Traditionally, and especially during the past 300 years (perhaps since 1700 or so, at least in the West, and since about that time in Japan as well), an educated person was somebody who had a prescribed stock of formal knowledge. The Germans called this knowledge *allgemeine Bildung*, and the English (and, following them, the nineteenth century Americans) called it the liberal arts. Increasingly, an educated person will be somebody who has learned how to learn, and who continues

learning, especially by formal education, throughout his or her lifetime” (Drucker 1994). Education and development are crucial in a knowledge society. P.F. Drucker concludes that “the next society will be a knowledge society. Knowledge will be its key resource, and knowledge workers will be the dominant group in its workforce” (Drucker 2001).

By definition, knowledge society contributes to the well-being of individuals and community. Subsequently, knowledge in this society is a driver of economic and social development. The European Union set its goal to become “the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world, capable of sustaining economic growth with more and better jobs and greater social cohesion” (Lisbon European Council 2000).

Knowledge economies are referred to as “knowledge-based economies – economies which are directly based on the production, distribution and use of knowledge and information” (OECD 1996: 7). Production, distribution and use of knowledge presuppose knowledge management that is “the explicit and systematic management of vital knowledge – and its associated processes of creation, organization, diffusion, use and exploitation” (Skyrme 1998: 8).

The policy of knowledge economy, knowledge society, is the promotion of innovation. It is defined as “the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, a new marketing method or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations” (OECD 2005: 46).

One of the major terms to be discussed is diplomacy, a central concept in the study of international relations and external relations of one’s country or organization. The concept comprises two approaches. In the narrow sense diplomacy is foreign policy (words before force). In a broader sense diplomacy is a process of negotiations and deliberations. In other words it is the art and practice of conducting negotiations and maintaining relations between nations in handling affairs by promoting peace and cooperation. In fact, diplomacy should be a dialogue among nations. Still there are a great number of international activities that do not cope with cooperation. Among them, J.C. de Magalhaes (1988) identifies unilateral acts such as propaganda, espionage, political or economic intervention, threat, deterrence, and economic war. Recently a new type of violence has been developed, the hybrid war orchestrated by Russia in Ukraine.

1. Knowledge Society Pillars

Europe is the cradle of the most powerful world civilization. Europe has known all development phases of human society. The history of Europe's peoples comprises several distinct types of socio-economic development: agricultural society (cyclic, seasonal), industrial society (linear, predictive), information society (information technology, networking), knowledge society (multiple scenarios, foresight).

European knowledge society is based on four pillars: education, ICT, innovation, and development. It is recognised the societal centrality of knowledge, identified in all pillars. The sustainability paradigm favours institutions, politics and the conditions for knowledge creation in a knowledge society. Moreover, the role of knowledge is quintessential in the economic growth of Europe.

The concept is enriched with the smart knowledge society: "to be a smart knowledge society, it is not enough to be rich in main assets and to take care of their development. A new sense of direction in development and a commitment to this new direction must assure high levels of ... quality of life and ... safety of life" (Bertucci 2005: 91). Knowledge society as a source of development should ultimately imply the quality and safety of life.

It can be said that Europe is better at producing high-level knowledge on the one hand. On the other hand, it faces difficulties at converting high-level knowledge into benefits of social and economic nature, taking into consideration great disparities between European countries and regions. Europe should use knowledge to innovate all its fields of activity. In this design a crucial role is played by universities. The academic world in a knowledge society should aim at producing innovations for community benefits.

1.1. Innovation Policy

An important step towards innovations in the European Union is *Innovation policy: updating the Union's approach in the context of the Lisbon strategy*. The act urges that "achieving an innovation performance that makes the European Union a world reference for innovation represents an enormous opportunity that can translate into raised living standards" (European Commission 2003: 4). Primarily, the act focuses on updating the concept of innovation: the multidimensional nature of the innovation phenomenon and the implications for the policy; the field of action of innovation policy; the current challenges for EU innovation policy; a coordinated framework for

innovation policy in the EU's context; and the new directions for European innovation policy development.

1.2. Innovation Union

The European Commission's act *Innovation Union* contains the idea that innovation leads to growth. The act answers the question why Europe needs an innovation union: to create job opportunities for all, especially the young; to get the economy back on track; to make companies more competitive in the global market; to solve the challenges of an ageing population; to secure resources like food and fuel; to fight global warming; to improve smart and green transport. The act argues that "Europe's future is connected to its power to innovate. The Innovation Union, an action-packed initiative for an innovation-friendly Europe, is the solution. It ... aims to create smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" (European Commission 2013: 2). The act provides the definition of the concept: "innovation is the ability of individuals, companies and entire nations to continuously create their desired future" (Kao 2007: 19). It tackles the issue of how the innovation union changes Europe, enumerating the benefits for European citizens. How the innovation union functions is to be presented by scoreboard indicators.

1.3. Knowledge Diplomacy

Knowledge diplomacy is a recently coined term referring to the new diplomacy in international relations. D. Johnston defines the diplomacy of knowledge as "ability and willingness to work together and share ... learning across disciplines and borders" (Johnston 2012). Knowledge diplomacy, continues D. Johnston, is based on three critical Cs: Creativity, Communication and Cooperation in international relations "for social benefit with the ultimate goal of making the world a better place for everyone ..., envisaging a world in which all nations (and all peoples) are eager to know and share their learning" (Johnston 2012). D. Johnston argues that knowledge diplomacy should "open up relationships between peoples at all levels and foster harmony in an interconnected world" (Johnston 2012). B. Kjellén (2007) states that "a basic feature of the new diplomacy is that actors other than foreign ministry officials become relatively more important than in traditional diplomacy in terms of interaction with other nations or with international organizations" (Sjöstedt 2009: 6).

Luc Vinet emphasizes that "in the past, a democratic, wealthy, militarily powerful country could count on having its voice heard on the international scene. Nowadays, a country's diplomatic effectiveness rests as much on the power of its institutions as

its consistent promotion of human rights and values” (Vinet 2008). Vinet underlines the role of university in developing the concept: “knowledge diplomacy, defined loosely, is the diplomacy of ideas, and ideas are the *raison d'être* of universities. ... Universities worldwide are collaborating with each other, multinational companies and governments, forging relationships that amount to a complementary diplomacy that works alongside that conducted at the state level” (Vinet 2008). Further he concludes: “by investing in knowledge diplomacy, we can ensure that our ideas, and the ideas of the bright academics we need to attract, have access to the best ideas of the wider world. Success would result in the rarest achievement in international diplomacy: a win-win situation” (Vinet 2008).

Knowledge diplomacy rethinks the actors, methods, tools, results of traditional diplomacy in an extensive manner. The uniting element of this entire concept is knowledge, which is of paramount importance in the knowledge society, both in its internal and external relations.

In knowledge diplomacy the experts “tend to take on an increasingly independent role in relation to the foreign ministry, whose supremacy in international affairs is therefore put at risk, at least over a long-term perspective. Other non-state actors have also become more important in the new diplomacy system. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have been given easier access to new diplomacy talks. This development is clearly visible in international environmental cooperation where NGOs have gradually taken on new tasks. For example, NGOs have provided important input information to some complex international negotiations and in other negotiations; they have been given formal monitoring tasks regarding the verification of state compliance with a binding international agreement. Businesses continue to be important players on many international arenas where states make their political choices” (Sjöstedt 2009: 6).

Knowledge diplomacy functions rather as a mediator and facilitator for traditional diplomacy fostering scientific knowledge in international relations, in international negotiations. Thus, knowledge diplomacy strives to consensual knowledge that “represents the common but specific understanding that parties have of the issues on the negotiation agenda” (Sjöstedt 2009: 5). The tendency for knowledge is captured by P.F. Drucker who mentions that “knowledge technologists are likely to become the dominant social – and perhaps also political – force over the next decades” (Drucker 2001).

Examples of good practices are the international talks on long-range air pollution, acid rains, in the context of United Nations. The most of Eastern and Western European states were formal parties to them. Canada and the United States were informal parties, but having a great influence on negotiation agenda. Leadership capabilities of Norway and Sweden resided in skilful knowledge diplomacy, because superior knowledge about

the long-range air pollution through acid rains was attained by multiple interested and concerned actors belonging to these countries.

The European Union supports financially joint projects of scientists, being nationals of various countries, to produce knowledge. This knowledge is produced in the framework of knowledge diplomacy, because it circulates and is shared in different countries, e.g. a greener Europe, a smarter economy, etc.

Internationalization of education, training and research by the European Union makes clear impulses for developing knowledge diplomacy.

Knowledge diplomacy is on the way to set other issues for the benefits of Europe and the world, for instance, new/innovative knowledge in climate warming, in fighting terrorism and criminality, in frozen and emerged conflicts, especially in Europe.

Instead of a concluding idea, it is worth mentioning that knowledge diplomacy should permeate not only informal diplomacy, but also formal diplomacy to achieve success, especially on vital and sensitive issues.

1.4. Knowledge Diplomacy: Challenges

It is more important to tackle the challenges for knowledge diplomacy as the world changes rapidly and people need swift solutions to the newly created realities.

The challenges are of horizontal and vertical nature. “An important challenge for the new diplomacy is to develop more effective mechanisms to cope with the so-called horizontal issues (e.g. trade/environment), linking the activities of different ministries and central agencies in any given setting, ... the assembly of institutions supporting the global negotiation on climate warming, or the machinery for policy coordination” (Sjöstedt 2009: 7).

The vertical challenge resides in how to identify mechanisms of cooperation between various hierarchical layers and actors both at national, regional and international levels. Another relevant question relates to the extent to which it is possible to attain consensual knowledge in more areas.

As a result of combining the horizontal and vertical challenges, it is fair to formulate a couple of questions which would describe the cooperation among various actors: which institutions need to be further developed (or created) in order to make new diplomacy more effective? How can new diplomacy support traditional diplomacy more effectively in complex international negotiations? How should the distribution of work between traditional and new diplomacy be organized best? (cf. G. Sjöstedt 2009).

On a practical level, Europe faces several challenges which refer to regional security. There are many sources of war over the European continent. The most

dangerous are those from Eastern Europe, because they are “open wounds”, affecting regional security.

A revival of negotiations on defence between North European countries – Poland, Finland, Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania – in the framework of NATO partnership is seen only in consequence of the Russian occupation policy in Ukraine. On the other hand, how will the United Kingdom face a potential conflict on the Falkland Islands with Argentina backed by Russia?

An obvious question arises: is it possible to implement knowledge diplomacy approaches? Is it possible to use knowledge diplomacy as a counterpart to Russia's aggressive diplomacy, coercive diplomacy, diplomacy of propaganda, diplomacy of disinformation?

It is worth mentioning the role of knowledge diplomacy for further negotiations to come up with answers to the following questions: why does Russia not respect international law? Why does Russia not respect the principle of territorial integrity? Why does Russia not respect the fundamental rights and freedoms of other peoples and of its own citizens? What are the interests of Russia as such in international relations? Has Russia defined its interests at all based on co-existence?

A solution to the “terrible child” in international relations, Russia, would be to apply knowledge diplomacy towards it by means of involving more actors, formal and informal participants: great and small states, interested and concerned public and private entities, including individuals to restore the international legal order.

The access to superior knowledge will enable interested parties to come up with diplomatic solutions during negotiations over conflicts in which Russia is directly involved, irrespective of whether it recognises them or not (it is a matter of political correctness in international relations).

The reinforcement of the EU knowledge diplomacy tools, their diversification and continuous adaptation in relations with problematic international actors. Unusual diplomatic behaviour would lead to the doorstep of war between civilizations and cultures (e.g. Russian media materials present western civilization and culture in the blackest paints, the western civilization versus the Russian civilization). Unfortunately, Russia has created a great gap in its relations with Europe and the rest of the world. The effects will be catastrophic. Ordinary citizens suffer from the ideology that is used to influence them at the moment. The effects will be extremely negative on their minds, as they will become predisposed to reject any normal external cooperation.

Thus, knowledge creation and knowledge transfer in all social spheres, public and private, internal and external affairs should be a strategic mission of the knowledge society. Science must play its undeniable role in international policymaking. The diffusion and migration of knowledge can only help traditional diplomacy. Digital

diplomacy as the use of ICT can help achieve diplomatic objectives. In this case, knowledge management is crucial in dealing with Wikis, blogs, instant messaging, SharePoint, and other collaborative technologies; inter-institutional cooperation; ICT supporting collaboration; social networking. In fact, all these transform diplomacy business practices.

The creation of knowledge and innovative approaches to its use and transfer at various layers of knowledge diplomacy can be considered a new dimension in external relations of the European Union and the Member States as well. Moreover, it is the basis for new diplomacy that will work for the benefit of people, for peace and human security.

2. Knowledge Diplomacy: Tools

Knowledge diplomacy needs great support and substantial contribution to be operational. The European Union increased the financing for actions in the field of education, research and innovation. It is a smart response to the knowledge society needs. For that reason, the European Union's tools of financing knowledge production and exploitation can be divided into universal programmes such as Erasmus+, Horizon 2020 and specialized ones, which are envisioned for individual areas.

3. Conclusions and Recommendations

The closing remarks are open conclusions and recommendations, susceptible to developing further debates on knowledge diplomacy. However, certain conclusions can be drawn. Knowledge diplomacy stands for a better opportunity to traditional diplomacy, a new dimension in shaping external and international relations.

Even knowledge diplomacy may appear a soft diplomacy; consensual results of knowledge diplomacy can produce a high degree of authority and acceptance among parties in international relations. Strategically, consensual knowledge has a two-fold feature; it both directs and constrains concerned parties.

The topics addressed in diplomatic practice need to be assessed in scientific terms for better understanding and for the negotiations' success. Knowledge management in multiparty talks speaks for the role of scientists and science in external relations

and in international cooperation. Therefore, knowledge diplomacy is diplomacy of cooperation.

Knowledge diplomacy is extremely open to innovations, competitiveness, knowledge and human mobility. Knowledge diplomacy serves economic growth, smart growth for sustainable development in the knowledge society, a society concerned with the growing quality of life.

Last but not the least, knowledge diplomacy is in best interest of peace.

Recommendations are rather potential tasks both for the academic world and diplomacy, as the study of international relations:

- knowledge diplomacy deserves priority in academic research and international negotiations;
- the establishment of enlarged partnership epistemic communities that is made up of policymakers, diplomats, businessmen and scientists in promoting a functional knowledge diplomacy, thereby reinforcing their role in international politics;
- the creation of multinational think-tanks on problematic issues in international relations, for example on recently initiated conflicts in Europe.

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